

Quality Data use for Strengthening Polio Eradication Program: Lessons from Nigeria and the Lake Chad Basin 2025.

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ABSTRACT

ARTICLE DETAILS

Background: Poliomyelitis remains a global public health priority due to its potential to cause irreversible paralysis. Despite Nigeria being declared free of wild poliovirus in 2020, the resurgence of circulating vaccine-derived poliovirus type 2 (cVDPV2) and persistent gaps in routine immunization coverage underscore the need for data-driven interventions. This study examines how quality data use strengthened routine immunization and cross-border surveillance within the polio eradication program in Nigeria and the Lake Chad Basin.

Methods: The study employed a multi-faceted, operational approach integrating standardized data collection, expanded joint analysis, and digital monitoring tools. Real-time data systems, geo-spatial mapping, and settlement-level microplanning were implemented across seven high-priority Nigerian states and 30 focus Local Government Areas (LGAs), in collaboration with cross-border stakeholders. Data were reviewed and harmonized to inform immunization planning, supervision, and outbreak response.

Results: Interventions improved vaccination coverage by reducing missed settlements, enhancing supportive supervision, and extending routine immunization reach to previously underserved or insecure areas. Real-time dashboards and supervision feedback loops facilitated timely corrective actions, while joint cross-border analysis enhanced collaboration, trust, and efficiency in campaign implementation. Geo-evidence-based mobilization enabled identification and vaccination of children in previously unrecorded settlements, demonstrating measurable improvements in both routine immunization and polio supplementary immunization activities.

Conclusions: Data-driven strategies, including standardized collection, real-time monitoring, and cross-border collaboration, substantially improved immunization outcomes and outbreak response in Nigeria and the Lake Chad Basin. Embedding these approaches into routine health system operations and prioritizing outreach to hard-to-reach populations can sustain gains in polio eradication and strengthen broader immunization programs.

KEYWORDS: Poliomyelitis; cVDPV2; immunization coverage; data-driven interventions; cross-border surveillance; Lake Chad Basin; Nigeria.

Published On:
09 May 2026

Available on:
<https://ijrsrs.org/>

INTRODUCTION

Poliomyelitis is a highly infectious viral disease caused by the poliovirus, primarily affecting children under five years of age and often resulting in irreversible paralysis or death (Kew et al., 2004). Since the launch of the Global Polio Eradication Initiative (GPEI) in 1988, global efforts have dramatically reduced the incidence of wild poliovirus (WPV), bringing the world closer than ever to eradication (Asghar et al., 2014). Nigeria, historically a major reservoir of WPV in Africa, achieved a landmark milestone when it

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was certified free of indigenous WPV in 2020 (Nasir et al., 2016). This achievement reflected decades of coordinated immunization campaigns, active surveillance, and robust political commitment.

Despite this success, the resurgence of circulating vaccine-derived poliovirus type 2 (cVDPV2) has underscored persistent vulnerabilities in the health system. Between 2020 and 2021, Nigeria experienced a dramatic increase in cVDPV2 cases, from 22 cases in seven states to over 1,028 cases in 31 states (Eze et al., 2025). These outbreaks highlight gaps in routine immunization coverage, weak surveillance in hard-to-reach populations, and limitations in health infrastructure (Ibrahim et al., 2024). The majority of cVDPV2 cases were concentrated in regions affected by insecurity, displacement, and poor access to health services, particularly across the Lake Chad (Bawa et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2025).

The Lake Chad Basin presents unique operational challenges that amplify the risk of poliovirus transmission. Cross-border population movements, conflicts, and environmental barriers impede routine immunization and limit timely detection of new cases, threatening the sustainability of polio eradication gains (Owoaje et al., 2020). These dynamics show the need for adaptive, cross-border strategies that strengthen both routine immunization systems and surveillance mechanisms, particularly in high-risk areas (Braka et al., 2023).

In response to these challenges, the National Primary Health Care Development Agency (NPHCDA), with support from international partners, has prioritized **data-driven interventions** to guide programmatic decision-making. Coordination through the National Emergency Operations Center (EOC), in collaboration with partners such as Solina Center for International Development and Research (SCIDaR), eHealth Africa, and the World Health Organization Regional Office for Africa (WHO AFRO), alongside other implementing and funding partners including the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF), has facilitated the implementation of integrated strategies that leverage real-time data, digital monitoring tools, and joint data analysis (Barau et al., 2014; Bello et al., 2021). These interventions are designed to improve the identification of high-risk populations, strengthen accountability in vaccination campaigns, and enhance the capacity for timely outbreak detection and response.

This article examines the impact of quality data use on strengthening routine immunization and cross-border surveillance in Nigeria and the Lake Chad Basin. We explore how data-informed interventions contributed to improved visibility, operational efficiency, and effectiveness in polio outbreak response, while also reinforcing broader immunization systems. Insights from this analysis provide practical lessons for regions facing similar epidemiological and operational challenges.

METHODS

Contextual Background

The Lake Chad Basin is a complex, transnational region spanning five countries: Nigeria, Chad, Cameroon, Niger, and the Central African Republic (Aisha & Adamu, 2024). The region is characterized by mobile populations, seasonal migration, conflict-related inaccessibility, and challenging terrain, all of which impede health service delivery and routine surveillance (Bigna, 2016; W et al., 2020). These conditions create persistent risks for poliovirus transmission and highlight the need for data-driven, coordinated interventions that can effectively operate across national boundaries (Owoaje et al., 2020).

Within this context, Nigeria, in collaboration with neighboring countries and international partners, implemented a structured approach to strengthen routine immunization and cross-border surveillance. The overarching goal was to generate timely, high-quality data that could inform decision-making at national, subnational, and local levels, particularly in high-risk and border-local government areas (LGAs) (Braka et al., 2023).

Data Use Approaches

The Nigerian polio program adopted three strategic, interlinked approaches to maximize the utility of available data for immunization and outbreak response:

1. **Standardizing Data Collection Tool**– Aimed at ensuring comparability, consistency, and reliability of data across borders. Standardization involved harmonizing indicators, aligning reporting formats, and integrating country-specific nuances to facilitate joint analysis (Okeibunor et al., 2016).
2. **Expanded Joint Analysis** – This approach convened multi-level teams (national, state, and LGA) to conduct collaborative evaluations of supplementary immunization activities (SIAs). Special emphasis was placed on border LGAs to identify shared vulnerabilities, detect gaps, and optimize resource allocation (Owoaje et al., 2020).
3. **Monitoring and Visualization Tools** – The use of digital dashboards and analytic platforms enabled real-time visibility of implementation progress. These tools provided stakeholders with actionable insights for timely decision-making, monitoring coverage, and tracking operational efficiency (Bello et al., 2021).

Data from field activities were systematically reviewed, harmonized, and analyzed using a combination of digital and geospatial techniques, including Nigeria's e-Tally system and settlement-level geo-tagging, to enhance accuracy, transparency, and accountability (Barau et al., 2014; Ngo-Bebe et al., 2025).

Strategic Interventions

Standardized Data Collection Tools

The intervention began with a systematic review of existing data collection instruments to identify inconsistencies and gaps across countries in the Lake Chad Basin. This process was coordinated by the Cross-Border Data Harmonization Task Force, which included representatives from Nigeria, Niger, and other neighboring countries (Aisha & Adamu, 2024). Through a series of regular consultations, stakeholders aligned data collection methodologies, harmonized indicators, and reconciled country-specific reporting protocols. This standardization facilitated comparability of data across borders, reduced discrepancies in reporting, and promoted co-learning among health teams, while ensuring compliance with national data governance policies (Aylward & Tangermann, 2011). By creating a common framework for data collection, this approach enhanced the reliability and validity of information used for cross-border immunization planning.

Expanded Analysis and Joint Evaluation

Building on standardized data, multi-level teams conducted joint evaluations of supplementary immunization activities (SIAs), with a focus on border LGAs where population mobility and operational overlap were highest (Owoaje et al., 2020). These collaborative evaluations enabled teams to identify shared vulnerabilities, optimize resource allocation, and implement targeted interventions in underserved areas. The joint analysis improved programmatic efficiency by integrating perspectives from multiple administrative levels, (Braka et al., 2023; Okeibunor et al., 2016). Additionally, the process facilitated the identification of missed settlements, informed supervisor deployment, and guided subsequent microplanning for immunization campaigns, ultimately enhancing coverage and effectiveness (Owoaje et al., 2020).

Monitoring Tool Implementation

To support real-time decision-making, digital monitoring and visualization tools were introduced and adapted to track the progress of joint work plans across borders. Dashboards provided actionable insights into the timeliness, quality, and completeness of field activities, while enabling stakeholders to monitor the implementation of joint operational plans at national, state, and local levels (Bello et al., 2021; Poy et al., 2017). These tools also enhanced visibility across coordination platforms, such as the Regional Lake Chad Basin (LCB) Coordination Platform, allowing program managers to rapidly identify gaps, adjust strategies, and improve accountability (Barau et al., 2014). The monitoring systems facilitated adaptive management by integrating multiple data sources. This ensures that both routine immunization and outbreak response interventions were guided by accurate, timely, and contextually relevant information (Ryman et al., 2011).

RESULTS

Nigeria-Specific Achievements

The interventions in Nigeria were concentrated in seven high-priority states, encompassing 30 focus Local Government Areas (LGAs), where dedicated data analyst support facilitated robust monitoring and evaluation of polio vaccination campaigns. Real-time data collection, notably through the e-Tally system, allowed program managers to track vaccination status at key points of interest, including community management of acute malnutrition (CMAM) sites and public markets. This timely information enabled rapid identification of gaps in coverage and informed immediate corrective actions during supplementary immunization activities (SIAs).

Geo-evidence-based mobilization strategies further strengthened outreach efforts by identifying previously unrecorded settlements, ensuring that children in these areas were included in vaccination campaigns. The integration of a supervision feedback loop, which linked field supervision data with performance outcomes, improved the quality of vaccination services and enhanced accountability across the targeted LGAs. Additionally, mapping of fixed-point immunization sites facilitated the delivery of routine immunization (RI) services in otherwise insecure or hard-to-reach settlements, extending the reach of vaccination efforts to vulnerable populations.

Improvements in Vaccination Reach

The combined effect of these interventions resulted in measurable improvements in vaccination coverage. Enhanced data use and geo-spatial tracking contributed to a significant reduction in missed settlements, ensuring that high-risk and previously underserved communities were reached. Supportive supervision was strengthened through real-time performance monitoring, enabling supervisors to target specific operational gaps and improve field-level practices. Collectively, these achievements demonstrate that the integration of standardized data collection, joint analysis, and digital monitoring tools can translate into tangible gains in immunization outcomes, both in routine services and in polio SIA campaigns.

DISCUSSION

This study demonstrates that leveraging high-quality, real-time data and cross-border collaboration can significantly strengthen routine immunization and polio surveillance in complex operational settings such as Nigeria and the Lake Chad Basin. The findings

Quality Data use for Strengthening Polio Eradication Program: Lessons from Nigeria and the Lake Chad Basin 2025.

align with the study's objectives of examining how data-driven interventions contribute to improved visibility, accountability, and effectiveness in vaccination campaigns and outbreak response.

Our results indicate that real-time data collection systems, such as e-Tally, and geo-spatial tools enabled rapid identification of previously unrecorded settlements and underserved populations. This approach reduced missed settlements and directly contributed to higher immunization coverage across targeted LGA (Barau et al., 2014; Ngo-Bebe et al., 2025). These findings are consistent with global evidence showing that the integration of digital health tools and geo-spatial mapping improves microplanning, optimizes field-level interventions, and enhances vaccination outcomes in hard-to-reach or conflict-affected (Bello et al., 2021; Oyugi et al., 2025; Poy et al., 2017).

The establishment of supervision feedback loops further strengthened accountability and performance monitoring. Linking time-stamped supervisory data with field outcomes allowed program managers to identify operational gaps in near real-time and adjust strategies accordingly (Mafigiri et al., 2021). Similar strategies have been documented in polio and other immunization programs globally, demonstrating that data-driven supervision enhances program quality and operational efficiency (Akinyemi et al., 2021). The Lake Chad Basin represents a region of high epidemiological risk due to population mobility, insecurity, and weak health system infrastructure (Bawa et al., 2018). Our findings highlight that expanded joint analysis and collaborative evaluations across national borders improved planning efficiency, reduced duplication of efforts, and fostered trust among subnational stakeholders. This reflects broader evidence that cross-border coordination is critical for controlling infectious disease transmission in regions with porous borders and high population movement (Owoaje et al., 2020) (Okeibunor et al., 2016). By harmonizing indicators, standardizing data collection, and conducting multi-level analyses, the program strengthened the quality of surveillance and facilitated targeted immunization interventions (Braka et al., 2023).

Beyond immediate outbreak response, these interventions also enhanced routine immunization services by extending coverage to previously inaccessible or underserved populations (Ongwae et al., 2017). This underscores the importance of embedding data-driven strategies within broader health system strengthening efforts. The Nigeria experience provides a model for other high-risk, resource-limited settings where conflict, mobility, or geographic barriers compromise routine immunization and disease surveillance (Bogale et al., 2024).

CONCLUSION

The integration of standardized data collection, real-time digital monitoring, and cross-border joint analysis substantially improved both routine immunization coverage and polio outbreak response in Nigeria and the Lake Chad Basin. These findings support the global emphasis on data-driven, adaptive strategies for polio eradication and offer practical lessons for implementing similar interventions in other high-risk regions. Future efforts should continue to prioritize high-frequency data use, strengthen cross-border collaboration, and embed these practices within routine health system operations to sustain gains in immunization coverage and disease surveillance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To sustain gains in polio eradication and routine immunization, it is critical to maintain and expand the use of real-time digital monitoring, geo-spatial mapping, and standardized data collection tools. Embedding these interventions into broader health system operations will ensure continuity beyond polio-specific campaigns, while targeted capacity building for data analysts and field supervisors can enhance the quality and timeliness of programmatic decision-making.

Cross-border collaboration should be institutionalized across Lake Chad Basin countries through joint planning, analysis, and coordination mechanisms. Prioritizing outreach to insecure, mobile, and underserved populations using geo-evidence-based microplanning can reduce missed settlements and address shared vulnerabilities, ultimately strengthening both routine immunization coverage and outbreak response.

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge the invaluable contributions of the national and state surveillance teams, laboratory networks, and field officers whose dedication and hard work made this analysis possible. We also sincerely appreciate the support of our partners, including the World Health Organization (WHO), UNICEF, Solina Center for International Development and Research (SCIDaR), and other collaborating organizations, for their continuous commitment and technical support.

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